

HYPOTHERMIA AS A PREDICTOR OF SEVERE SEPSIS IN CHILDREN

Jumoboyev Ilyosbek Juraqul ugli
Teshaboyev Umidjon Mahamatjon ugli
Andijan State Medical Institute.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19972039>

Relevance. Sepsis is one of the main causes of child mortality: approximately 3.4 million children die from it worldwide annually [1].

International recommendations from the Surviving Sepsis Campaign emphasize the importance of early identification of risk factors for adverse outcomes in sepsis [3].

Hypothermia ($\leq 35.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) is considered one of the important predictors of severe sepsis [2,4].

Objective: to determine the prognostic value of hypothermia as an independent risk factor for adverse outcomes in children with sepsis.

Materials and methods. Cohort studies, meta-analyses, and international clinical recommendations for studying the relationship between temperature status and sepsis outcomes in children were analyzed.

Body temperature at admission and 28-day survival were assessed.

Results. In the multi-center prospective study by Kushimoto et al., hypothermia ($\leq 35.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) in severe sepsis is associated with a significantly increased risk of 28-day mortality: OR=3.096 (95% CI 1.549–6.189; $p=0.001$) [2].

Pathogenetically, hypothermia in sepsis is associated with the release of the CIRP protein (inflammatory mediator - DAMP), which through TLR4 receptors initiates a hyperimmune inflammatory response ("cytokin storm"), exacerbating multi-organ dysfunction [5].

In contrast, high fever ($38-39.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) is associated with the lowest mortality rate, reflecting an adequate immune response [4].

Conclusion. Hypothermia serves as a clinically significant independent predictor of adverse outcomes in sepsis in children and must be included in risk stratification algorithms.

SOURCES:

1. Rudd K.E., Johnson S.C., Agesa K.M. et al. Global, regional, and national sepsis incidence and mortality, 1990–2017: analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study // *The Lancet*. 2020. Vol. 395, № 10219. P. 200-211.
2. Kushimoto S., Gando S., Saitoh D. et al. The impact of body temperature abnormalities on the disease severity and outcome in patients with severe sepsis: an analysis from a multicenter, prospective survey of severe sepsis // *Critical Care*. 2013. Vol. 17, № 6. R271.
3. S.L. Weiss et al. Surviving Sepsis Campaign International Guidelines for the Management of Septic Shock and Sepsis-Associated Organ Dysfunction in Children // *Pediatric Critical Care Medicine*. – 2020. – Vol. 21, № 2. – P. e52–e106.
4. Rumbus Z., Matics R., Hegyi P. et al. Fever is associated with reduced, hypothermia with increased mortality in septic patients: a meta-analysis of clinical trials // *PLOS ONE*. 2017. Vol. 12, № 1. e0170152.

Aprel, 2026-yil

5. Qiang X., Yang W.L., Wu R. et al. Cold-inducible RNA-binding protein (CIRP) triggers inflammatory responses in hemorrhagic shock and sepsis // Nature Medicine. 2013. Vol. 19, № 11. P. 1489-1495.

MODERN SCIENCE
& RESEARCH